

Fatigue of Composite Bolted Joints under Dual Load Levels

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ABSTRACT

A fatigue and residual strength degradation model has been applied to predict the fatigue life distribution of composite bolted joints under dual load levels. An experimental test program using composite bolted joints with $[+45^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ]_{3S}$ and $[+45^\circ/0^\circ_2]_{3S}$ lay-ups has been carried out to generate statistical data for verifying the proposed approach. It is shown that the correlation between the test results and the theoretical predictions of the fatigue life distribution under dual load levels is very reasonable.

INTRODUCTION

The application of composite materials to airframe structures, both primary and secondary, is very promising because of their superior performance when compared with metallic materials. As a result, an intensive research effort has been conducted in the last decade. One important aspect in the design of composite airframe structures is the fatigue characterization of composite materials, in particular the bolted and/or bonded joints. It has been shown (1-3) that the Miner's rule fails to predict the fatigue behavior of composite bolted or bonded joints under service loading spectra. It was suggested (1-3) that the fatigue behavior of composite joints should be based on the test results under given design loading spectra. In this connection, an extensive test program has been carried out recently to study the fatigue sensitivity of both the bolted and bonded composite joints with respect to the variation of loading spectra (4). The main disadvantage of the aforementioned approach is that the fatigue tests have to be performed under different service loading spectra and the test results can not be translated from one loading spectrum to another.

The purpose of this paper is aimed at the development of a more basic approach to predict the fatigue behavior under spectrum loading from some base-line constant amplitude fatigue test results. A fatigue and residual strength degradation model previously proposed for advanced composite laminates (e.g., 5-6) is applied herein to predict the fatigue life distribution of composite bolted joints under dual loads.

A test program using AS1/3501-6 graphite/epoxy bolted joints was carried out to generate base-line constant amplitude fatigue data and static ultimate

strength data. These data sets were used to determine the parameter values involved in the fatigue model. Then, the statistical figure life data under dual load levels were generated to demonstrate the applicability of the theoretical fatigue model. It is shown that the correlation between the test results and the predictions based on the fatigue model is very reasonable.

STATISTICAL FATIGUE MODEL

The static ultimate strength $R(0)$ is a random variable assumed to follow the two-parameter Weibull distribution with the shape parameter α and the scale parameter β (5,6)

$$F_{R(0)}(x) = P[R(0) \leq x] = 1 - \exp\{-(x/\beta)^\alpha\} \quad ; \quad x \geq 0 \quad (1)$$

A fatigue and residual strength degradation model under constant amplitude cyclic loading proposed in Refs. 5-6 is expressed as follows;

$$R^c(n_1) = R^c(n_0) - \beta^c K S^b (n_1 - n_0) \quad (2)$$

in which $R(n_1)$ and $R(n_0)$ are the residual strengths at n_1 and n_0 load cycles ($n_1 > n_0$), respectively; b , c and K are three parameters to be determined from base-line data; S is the stress (or load) range defined as $S = (1-R)\sigma_{\max}$ where σ_{\max} represents the maximum cyclic stress (or load) and R is the stress ratio. Equation 2 indicates that the residual strength at n_1 load cycles is expressed in terms of the residual strength at the previous load cycles n_0 and other loading parameters. Furthermore, the characteristic fatigue life \bar{N} under the constant amplitude cyclic loading is expressed in terms of the classical $S-N$ expression in Refs. 5-6 as $K S^b \bar{N} = 1$ or $\bar{N} = 1/K S^b$.

For $n_0 = 0$ and $n_1 = n$, Eq. 2 reduces to

$$R^c(n) = R^c(0) - \beta^c K S^b n \quad (3)$$

Fatigue Life Distribution Under Dual Loads

The fatigue and residual strength degradation model given by Eq. 2 can be used to predict the effect of load sequence on the distributions of the fatigue life and the residual strength. For simplicity, we shall consider the fatigue life distribution under a sequence of dual stress (or load) levels. Let the specimen be subjected to a sequence of two cyclic loadings, with constant stress ratio, R , and maximum stresses (loads) $\sigma_{1\max}$ and $\sigma_{2\max}$, respectively, for n_1 and n_2 cycles. If the number of load cycles n_2 under the second fatigue loading is increased until the specimen fails, then the fatigue life, N_{12} , denoting the number of load cycles to failure under the second load, is a statistical variable.

The distribution function $F_{N_{12}}(n) = P[N_{12} \leq n]$ of N_{12} is derived from Eqs. 1-3 in the Appendix; with the result (see also 6)

$$F_{N_{12}}(n) = 1 - \exp \left\{ - \left[\frac{n}{\bar{N}_2} + \frac{n_1}{\bar{N}_1} + \left(\frac{\sigma_{2\max}}{\beta} \right)^c \right]^{a/c} \right\} \quad (4)$$

in which the characteristic fatigue lives under $\sigma_{1\max}$ and $\sigma_{2\max}$, denoted by \bar{N}_1 and \bar{N}_2 , respectively, are given by

$$\bar{N}_1 = 1/K S_1^b, \quad \bar{N}_2 = 1/K S_2^b \quad (5)$$

Equation 4 is a three-parameter Weibull distribution with a negative lower bound at $-[n_1(\bar{N}_2/\bar{N}_1) + \bar{N}_2(\sigma_{2\max}/\beta)^c]$. Such a negative lower bound stems from the fact that the specimen may fail either under the first cyclic loading or under the first cycle of the second fatigue loading.

The probability of failure under the first fatigue loading, denoted by P_{12} , can be obtained from Eq. 4 by setting $n=0$ and replacing $\sigma_{2\max}$ by $\sigma_{1\max}$ as follows

$$P_{12} = 1 - \exp \left\{ - \left[\frac{n_1}{\bar{N}_1} + \left(\frac{\sigma_{1\max}}{\beta} \right)^c \right]^{a/c} \right\} \quad (6)$$

The fatigue model given by Eq. 2 is reasonable when the degradation rate of the residual strength is slow for small number of load cycles n . For situations where the degradation rate is fast, generalized fatigue models were proposed in Refs. 7-8. These generalized models degenerate into Eq. 2 as a special case when the degradation rate of the residual strength is assumed to be slow for small n . However, these models involve additional parameters which should be determined from residual strength test results under constant amplitude cyclic loading. Since the base-line residual strength data are not available, attempt is made herein to apply the more restrictive fatigue model as given by Eq. 2 to the fatigue behavior of composite bolted joints.

Determination of Model Parameters

The fatigue model given by Eqs. 1-2 involves parameters α , β , c , b and K , which should be determined from base-line test results. Then the fatigue model is capable of predicting the distribution of the fatigue life under dual stress (load) levels as shown in Eq. 4. The required base-line test data are described in the following; (i) One set of static ultimate strength data: The ultimate strength data set is used to estimate the shape parameter α and the scale parameter β of the Weibull distribution, Eq. 1. (ii) One set of constant amplitude fatigue data: The constant amplitude fatigue data under different maximum cyclic stresses (or loads) are used to establish the approximate S-N curve, i.e., $\bar{N}=1/KS^b$. This data set is converted into the equivalent static ultimate strength using the fatigue model of Eq. 3, and then its statistical properties are matched with those of the static ultimate strength data set to determine the values of c , b and K . The detailed procedures for estimating the c , b and K values are described in Refs. 5-6. It should be mentioned that in the constant amplitude fatigue tests, the fatigue life may be too long, e.g., exceeding 2×10^6 cycles, when the stress (or load) range is too small. In such a situation the fatigue test can be terminated and the residual strength should be measured. The residual strength data is as useful as the fatigue life data in estimating c , b and K values (see 5-6).

TEST RESULTS AND CORRELATION

Test Specimen and Procedures

The configuration of the specimen used in the test program is illustrated in Figure 1. When supported against out of plane deflections, as all specimens were during testing, the specimen is typical of aircraft joints. The specimen geometry with $e/D=3.0$, $s/D=5.2$ and $t/D=.5$ are representative of current composite joint design practice, where D =hole diameter, e =distance from the center of the hole to the edge of the specimen, s =distance between fastener holes and t =laminate thickness. Titanium K-lobe fasteners and A286 collars were used.

Fig. 1: Specimen Geometry (Dimension in inches)

The fastener holes were drilled with gun-drill bits in conjunction with a Quackenbush drill motor. Aluminum plate backup and a feed rate of .005 inches/revolution were used. All testing was conducted in the computer controlled test machine. Load-deflection curves were generated during each static test. All static test specimens failed in bearing. The fatigue tests were conducted at a cyclic rate of 5 cps to minimize the effect of heat-up. A linear variable displacement transducer (LVDT) was mounted between the machine loading heads to provide the failure indication. At intervals throughout the fatigue tests load cycling was stopped and the specimen was loaded statically to the maximum load in the spectrum and then to the minimum. The LVDT reading was taken at each load level and then plotted as a function of fatigue cycles. An increase in this curve is interpreted as hole elongation, and the point at which the increase becomes non-linear is defined as joint failure. This failure criteria

was developed and has been used successfully by two independent researchers (see 9 and 10). All fatigue failures were due to hole elongation.

Joints with $[+45^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ]_{3S}$ Lay-up

Thirteen [13] tests were performed to determine the static ultimate strength of the bolted joints. The average of the test results is 7.194 ksi (32.0 kN). The Weibull distribution given in Eq. 1 was used to fit the data yielding

$$\alpha = 37.8 \quad , \quad \beta = 7.3 \text{ kips (32.472 kN)} \quad (7)$$

These static data points are displayed in Fig. 2(a) as open circles along with the fitted Weibull distribution indicated by the solid curve.

Fig. 2: Distribution of Ultimate Strength for Bolted Joint With $[+45^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ]_{3S}$ Lay-Up; (a) Ultimate Strength, and (b) Converted Ultimate Strength

Fig. 3: Constant Amplitude Fatigue Life of Bolted Joint With $[+45^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ]_{3S}$ Lay-Up

A set of twenty-one [21] constant amplitude fatigue life data under different maximum load levels was generated. The results are presented in Fig. 3. For all the fatigue tests the loading frequency is 5 Hz and the load ratio is equal to -1, i.e., $R=-1$. Both the static ultimate strength data, Fig. 2(a), and the constant amplitude fatigue life data, Fig. 3, were used to determine the values of c , b and K ; with the results

$$c = 35.255 \quad , \quad b = 12.48 \quad , \quad K = 0.15 \times 10^{-12} (1.221 \times 10^{-21}) \quad (8)$$

in which the unit of $R(0)$, $R(n)$ and the load range S is in kips. If the unit of these quantities is in kN, the K value is given in the parenthesis.

The twenty-one fatigue life data were converted into the equivalent static ultimate strength using the fatigue model, Eq. 3, and the values of c , b and K given in Eq. 8. They are shown in Fig. 2(b) as open circles. Also shown in Fig. 2(b) as a solid curve is the Weibull distribution shown in Fig. 2(a) to indicate the confidence of the estimated c , b and K values.

After the values of α , β , c , b and K have been determined in Eqs. 7 and 8, the fatigue model is capable of predicting the fatigue life distribution under dual load levels as given by Eq. 4.

One set of twelve specimens was subjected to the first fatigue loading with the maximum load $\sigma_{1max}=1.85$ kips (8.229 kN) and $R=-1$ for $n_1=40,000$ cycles. Then the specimens were further subjected to the second fatigue loading with the maximum load $\sigma_{2max}=2.35$ kips (10.453 kN) and $R=-1$ until failure occurs.

In this test series two specimens failed before the end of the first cyclic loading.

According to the fatigue model given by Eq. 6, the probability of failure of a specimen under the first cyclic loading is computed as $p_{12}=0.06$. Hence, the average number of specimens to fail under the first fatigue loading is $N=0.06 \times 12 = 0.72$ specimen. Test results indicate two failures.

Fig. 4: Correlation Between Test Results and Theoretical Prediction of Fatigue Life Under Dual Load Levels; (a) $\sigma_{1max}=1.85$ kips, $n_1=40,000$ cycles, $\sigma_{2max}=2.35$ kips, and (b) $\sigma_{1max}=1.95$ kips, $n_1=17,000$ cycles, $\sigma_{2max}=2.35$ kips.

Test results of the fatigue life under the second fatigue loading are plotted in Fig. 4(a) as open circles. The fatigue life distribution based on the theoretical model given by Eq. 4 is depicted in Fig. 4(a) as a solid curve to show its correlation with the test results.

Another set of 12 specimens was subjected to a sequence of dual loads in which $\sigma_{1max}=1.95$ kips (8.694 kN), $n_1=17,000$ cycles, $\sigma_{2max}=2.35$ kips (10.453 kN) and $R=-1$. Based on Eq. 6, the probability that a specimen will fail before the second fatigue loading is computed as $p_{12}=0.048$. Hence, the average number of specimens to fail is $N=0.048 \times 12 = 0.58$. Test data show no failure at all. Test results of the fatigue life under σ_{2max} are plotted in Fig. 4(b) as open circles. The solid curve displayed in Fig. 4(b) is the theoretical prediction based on Eqs. 4, 7 and 8.

Based on the fatigue model the average number of specimens to fail under the first fatigue loading for two data sets (a total of 24 specimens) presented above is therefore $N=0.72+0.58=1.3$ specimens. Test results show a total of 2 failures. Such a slight discrepancy between the theory and the test results due to the sampling fluctuation is to be expected. It is observed from Fig. 4 that the correlation between the test results (open circles) and the theoretical predictions (solid curves) is very reasonable.

Joints With $[\pm 45^\circ/0^\circ]_{3S}$ Lay-Up

Eleven [11] tests were carried out to determine the static ultimate strength of the bolted joint. The average static ultimate strength of the test results is 6.286 kips (27.96 kN). Again, the Weibull distribution, Eq. 1, was used to fit the data resulting in

$$\alpha = 37.424 \quad , \quad \beta = 6.3794 \text{ kips (28.377 kN)} \quad (9)$$

These static data points are presented in Fig. 5(a) as open circles along with the best fitted Weibull distribution as indicated by the solid curve.

Fig. 5: Distribution of Ultimate Strength for Bolted Joint With $[+45^\circ/0^\circ]_{3S}$ Lay-Up; (a) Ultimate Strength and (b) Converted Ultimate Strength

Fig. 6: Constant Amplitude Fatigue Life for Bolted Joint With $[+45^\circ/0^\circ]_{3S}$ Lay-Up

A set of thirty-four [34] constant amplitude fatigue life data under different maximum loads with $R=-1$ was generated. The results are shown in Fig. 6. In Fig. 6 four specimens were fatigue tested over 10^6 cycles without failure as shown by triangles, and hence their residual strengths were measured and indicated in parentheses. From Figs. 5(a) and 6, we obtain

$$c = 31.02, \quad b = 15.563, \quad K = 0.2261 \times 10^{-15} (1.847 \times 10^{-26}) \quad (10)$$

Again the unit of $R(0)$, $R(n)$ and S is in kips and the value of K is given in the parenthesis if the unit is in kN. The converted equivalent ultimate strengths from the fatigue life data are plotted in Fig. 5(b) as circles. The solid curve shown in Fig. 5(b) is identical to that of Fig. 5(a) to indicate the confidence of the estimated c , b and K values.

Three sets of data with a sample size of 4, 9 and 12, respectively, were subjected to different dual load test conditions as follows; (i) $\sigma_{1max}=2.19$ kips, $n_1=65,000$ cycles and $\sigma_{2max}=2.442$ kips, (ii) $\sigma_{1max}=2.19$ kips, $n_1=40,000$ cycles and $\sigma_{2max}=2.64$ kips, and (iii) $\sigma_{1max}=2.4$ kips, $n_1=18,000$ cycles and $\sigma_{2max}=2.64$ kips.

Based on the fatigue model of Eq. 6, the probabilities of failure of a specimen under the first fatigue loading, p_{12} , are computed as 0.09, 0.051 and 0.106, respectively, for the three sets of data. The average numbers of specimens to fail under the first fatigue loading are, respectively, $N=0.09 \times 4=0.36$, $N=0.051 \times 9=0.46$ and $N=0.106 \times 12=1.27$. Hence the average number of failures for all three data sets is $N=0.36+0.46+1.27=2.09$ specimens. Test results indicate a total of 2 failures in the third data set.

The test results of the fatigue life under the second cyclic loading are plotted in Figs. 7(a)-7(c), respectively, as open circles for each data set. Also presented in these figures as solid curves are the corresponding distributions based on the fatigue model given by Eq. 4. It is observed that the correlation between the test results and the theoretical predictions shown in Figs. 7(a)-7(c) is very reasonable.

CONCLUSION

A fatigue and residual strength degradation model proposed in the literature for advanced composite laminates has been applied to describe the fatigue behavior of composite bolted joints under dual load levels. An experimental test program using two types of graphite/epoxy bolted joints, i.e., $[+45^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ]_{3S}$ and $[+45^\circ/0^\circ]_{3S}$, has been carried out to generate statistically meaningful fatigue life data. It is shown that the correlation between the

theoretical predictions based on the fatigue model and the test results, for the fatigue life distribution under dual load levels, is very reasonable.

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Fig. 7: Correlation Between Test Results and Theoretical Prediction for Fatigue Life Under Dual Loads; (a) $\sigma_{1max}=2.19$ kips, $n_1=65,000$ cycles, $\sigma_{2max}=2.442$ kips, (b) $\sigma_{1max}=2.19$ kips, $n_1=40,000$ cycles, $\sigma_{2max}=2.64$ kips, and (c) $\sigma_{1max}=2.4$ kips, $n_1=18,000$ cycles, $\sigma_{2max}=2.64$ kips.

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APPENDIX

The residual strength $R(n_1)$ after the application of the first fatigue loading can be expressed in terms of the ultimate strength $R(0)$ using Eq. 3,

$$R^c(n_1) = R^c(0) - \beta^c K S_1^b n_1 \quad (11)$$

in which $S_1 = (1-R)\sigma_{1\max}$ is the stress range of the first load. After the second cyclic loading is applied, the residual strength at n_1+n_2 load cycles, i.e., at the end of a sequence of two cyclic loadings, denoted by $R(n_1+n_2)$, can be expressed in terms of $R(n_1)$ using Eq. 2 as follows;

$$R^c(n_1+n_2) = R^c(n_1) - \beta^c K S_2^b n_2 \quad (12)$$

in which $S_2 = (1-R)\sigma_{2\max}$ is the stress (or load) range of the second load.

Adding Eq. 11 to Eq. 12, one obtains the residual strength $R(n_1+n_2)$ in terms of the ultimate strength $R(0)$,

$$R^c(n_1+n_2) = R^c(0) - \beta^c K (S_1^b n_1 + S_2^b n_2) \quad (13)$$

Thus, the statistical distribution of the residual strength $R(n_1+n_2)$ after a sequence of two cyclic loadings can be derived from that of $R(0)$ given by Eq. 1 (see Refs. 5 and 6).

Let the number of load cycles n_2 under the second fatigue loading be increased until the specimen fails, then the fatigue life N_{12} , denoting the number of load cycles to failure under the second load, is a statistical variable. The fatigue failure is assumed to occur when the residual strength $R(n_1+n_2)$ is reduced to the applied stress (load) level $\sigma_{2\max}$, i.e.,

$$R(n_1+n_2) = \sigma_{2\max} \quad \text{and} \quad n_2 = N_{12} \quad (14)$$

Substituting the failure condition of Eq. 14 into Eq. 13 and solving for the fatigue life N_{12} , one obtains

$$N_{12} = [R^c(0) - \sigma_{2\max}^c - \beta^c K S_1^b n_1] / \beta^c K S_2^b \quad (15)$$

in which the characteristic fatigue lives \tilde{N}_1 and \tilde{N}_2 are given by Eq. 5. Thus the distribution function of N_{12} can be derived easily from that of $R(0)$ through the transformation of Eq. 15 and the result is given by Eq. 4 (see 6).